

Can the fragment molecular orbital method predict the activity of inhibitor drugs?

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Abstract:

Improving the activity of lead compound is the most important task for any of the drug discovery program. In order to shorten the development period and reduce the cost, predicting the activity of the compounds reliably through computational approach is required. At present, it has been done mostly by calculating the binding score by the docking method using classical mechanics (CM) which can be carried out rapidly. However, since CM ignores electron correlation, results based on CM are inaccurate. Especially, CM cannot handle hydrophobic interactions that play vital role in ligand bindings. Contrarily, fragment molecular orbital (FMO) approach is an excellent quantum mechanical method using which large molecular systems, such as proteins, can be studied. It is a fragmentation method, in which a system is subdivided into fragments and the calculations are performed on each fragment separately. In the two-body method, FMO2, calculations are performed on fragment pairs (dimers) too. Interfragment interaction energies derived from these calculations are then used to analyze the molecular recognition, in particular, of ligands by proteins. FMO method has been successfully applied to study various protein-ligand interactions.¹ In the present study, we investigated the ability of the FMO method in predicting the activity of the drugs. For this purpose, we quantitatively studied the interactions of dipeptidyl peptidase IV (DPP-4) with its inhibitor drugs using FMO approach. DPP-4 is an enzyme responsible for the degradation of incretins which stimulate insulin secretion and so inhibition of DPP-4 becomes a proven method for the treatment of type 2 diabetics. All the calculations were performed using GAMESS program. The FMO2-MP2/6-31G(d) level of theory was used. To describe protein upon solvation, polarizable continuum model (PCM) was used in the FMO2-PCM method. Various approaches in PCM as well as in FMO, including subsystem analysis,³ were utilized for the calculations. The obtained interfragment interaction energies and binding energies were compared with the available experimental values (IC₅₀, K_D, K_i, and ΔH).

Our calculations indicate that FMO calculations can positively predict the inhibitor activity of the DPP-4 inhibitors. Especially, binding energies derived using FMO2-PCM subsystem analysis correlate better with the experimental activities of the drugs.

Keywords:

Fragment molecular orbital method, dipeptidyl peptidase IV (DPP-4), interfragment interaction energy, subsystem analysis, binding energy.

Figure 1: Binding energies obtained using FMO-PCM subsystem analysis for the case of DPP-4/alogliitin complex.

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Role of Analytical Techniques in Herbal Drugs- A Paradim

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Abstract:

In today's era were the utilization of herbal products and drugs are to its maximum the standardization with respect to the drugs still lacks the fundamental knowledge about its genuine. Thus is paper will focus on various parameters pertaining to the authenticity and its wereabout by meams of standardization and analytical techniques which are used for the detection of adulteration. Lack of proper standard parameters for the standardization of herbal preparation and several instances of substandard herbs, adulterated herbs come into existence. To meet new thrust of inquisitiveness, standardization of herbals is mandatory. Hence every single component present in herb needs to be quality checked to ascertain that it confirms to quality requirement and delivers the properties consistently. Standardization assures that products are reliable in terms of quality, efficacy, performance and safety. It is however observed that the drugs in commerce are frequently adulterated and do not comply with the standards prescribed for authentic drug. This is mainly due to the chemistry of the plant constituents which are present in it but still exact exploration is not at the most. Certain evaluation techniques like morphology, microscopical, chemical and biological techniques are used still its identify from different species becomes difficult with respect to the constituents. Hence a shophisticated technique by the use if instrumentation will guide us the process of qualitative and quantitative approach of the plant constituents were intruments like UV, FTIR, Mass, HPLC, HPTLC, LC-MS-MS, GC-MS, hypernated techniques etc are used for providing the standards and identity of the constituents. Hence it cab be illustrated that the progress on quality control of herbal medicines are just at its beginning stage where lot of efforts are to put in to for the excat constituent identification by these process. of a long journey. Hence the use of chromatographic fingerprints of herbal medicines are much moreessentail for its fingerprinting before confirming the presence of the moiety. However, using the chemical fingerprints for the purpose of quality control of herbal medicines can only address to the problem of comparing the integrated sameness and/or difference and controlling their stability of the available herbal products. So this paper will be informative in terms of providing the techniques available for identification and characterization of natural components.

Keywords:

Hebal drugs, Standardization, Analytical Techniques, Evaluation and Chemical Moeity.

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Towards the synthesis of a Leucine rich hexapeptide from *Stellaria dichotoma* L.

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Abstract:

The present investigation reports the synthesis of a Leucine rich N-methylated cyclopeptide, Dichotomin J, previously isolated from the roots *Stellaria dichotoma* L. of accomplished through the coupling of N-methylated tetrapeptide and dipeptide fragments followed by cyclization of the linear hexapeptide unit. Structure elucidation of the newly synthesized cyclopolypeptide was performed by means of FT-IR, ¹H-NMR and fast atom bombardment mass spectrometry (FABMS) and screened for its antibacterial, anthelmintic and cytotoxic potential. According to the antimicrobial activity results, the newly synthesized N-Methylated cyclopeptide exhibited potent antibacterial activity against Gram-negative bacteria, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and gram-positive bacteria *B. Subtilis* and antifungal activity against dermatophytes *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* and *Candida Albicans* at a concentration of 10 µg/mL, in comparison to the reference drugs, ciprofloxacin and griseofulvin. In addition, cyclopolypeptide displayed suitable levels of cytotoxicity against Dalton's lymphoma ascites (DLA) and Ehrlich's ascites carcinoma (EAC) cell lines.